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The Role of Good Governance and Gender Equality in Reducing Poverty: A Case Study of Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the role of good governance in the Pakistani economy, particularly in relation to increasing female labor force participation, implementing pro-poor and pro-growth public policies, and breaking the cycle of poverty. The primary objective of this study is to analyze a time series dataset covering the period from 1996 to 2022. To conduct the empirical analysis, the study employs robust regression, Granger causality tests, Impulse Response Function analysis, and Variance Decomposition Analysis. The results of the study reveal several significant findings. Firstly, government effectiveness and government regulatory quality demonstrates a positive and statistically significant relationship with poverty incidence. Further there is a positive relationship between unemployment rate and poverty incidence in a country. Conversely, variables such as female labor force participation rate, income equality, and economic growth exhibit a negative association with poverty incidence. This suggests that a higher level of government effectiveness, increased female labor force participation, more equitable income distribution, and higher per capita GDP can contribute to poverty reduction. The Granger causality tests indicate that there exists a unidirectional relationship between all governance and economic variables. Furthermore, the Variance Decomposition Analysis suggests that an increase in the female labor force participation rate is likely to lead to higher poverty levels. The Impulse Response Function also indicates that governance indicators, characterized by high corruption, poor regulatory quality, and inadequate government effectiveness, are likely to exacerbate poverty. In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of improving governance quality in order to reduce gender inequality, increase income levels, promote economic growth, and alleviate poverty. Addressing these issues at all levels of society is crucial for achieving sustainable development and poverty reduction in a country.

Keywords: Good governance; Gender equality; Poverty incidence; Pro-poor growth; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2015, a collective effort was undertaken by 195 nations to address the challenge of extreme poverty and promote shared prosperity worldwide. Eliminating poverty and achieving zero hunger pose significant and prominent challenges, particularly in developing countries. According to the World Bank, individuals in low-income countries allocate approximately two-thirds of their income towards meeting their basic food needs, while individuals in high-income countries spend around 25% of their income on such necessities. Over the past 25 years, the daily wage per person has remained at \$1.90. In 2019, a new disease called the coronavirus (COVID-19) emerged, and its rapid spread was primarily attributed to social gatherings.

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To curb the spread of the pandemic, lockdown measures were implemented worldwide. As a consequence of these measures, a significant number of people lost their jobs, experienced reduced income, work stoppages, especially among women, youth, individuals engaged in low-wage and informal work, and households living in poverty (World Bank Report, 2022). In the past three years, the various waves of the COVID-19 pandemic have had a negative impact on household income and consumption patterns. The World Bank report indicates that globally, between 40 million and 60 million people have fallen below the poverty line due to disruptions in the supply chain, a rise in inflation rates, increased unemployment, loss of foreign investments, and a decline in remittances (Economic Survey of Pakistan, 2021).

Economic development and growth are crucial in addressing extreme poverty. Ensuring equal opportunities and equitable wages for both men and women, including those from poor families, is essential. Productive and creative economic development is vital for the survival of any society. Economic expansion opens up a wide range of opportunities for all members of society, improves welfare, and reduces disparities between the poor and the rich, both within countries and among different nations. However, developing countries face challenges in achieving sustainable development due to factors such as high population growth rates, unaffordable expenditure costs, underdeveloped internal financial institutions, limited access to finance, and the mismanagement of natural resources (Hastuti & Udjiyanto, 2021). Social scientists argue that globalization has brought about significant changes in the international economy and world politics. Economists have observed that globalization promotes the free movement of goods and services within regions and across countries. It also enhances the mobility of labor and capital, leading to overall economic growth, albeit not necessarily an increase in per capita income. Globalization can reduce transportation and communication costs, facilitate capital inflows, foster market competition, and strengthen relationships between traders, financial flows, and the mobility of workers worldwide. However, varying degrees of heterogeneity in the global economy can lead to development gaps and negative impacts on individuals, exacerbating income inequality within and between countries (Heshmati, 2005).

Poverty alleviation is a significant challenge for all developing countries as it is crucial for achieving their development goals. The World Bank has established a benchmark, considering individuals below the poverty line when their per capita income falls below \$2. Poverty and income inequality stem from a lack of equal economic opportunities and gender disparities. Additionally, policies that favor the wealthy and unequal wealth distribution contribute to limited human development. Implementing pro-poor policies that focus on enhancing human capital through public investments can increase per capita income, reduce income inequality, and enable individuals to meet their basic needs, such as food, healthcare, and shelter. This, in turn, improves working conditions, productivity, and overall economic development (Ogbeide & Agu, 2005).

Approximately 75 percent of global poverty is concentrated in rural areas. Economists argue that the agricultural sector plays a crucial role in reducing poverty in developing countries. A significant portion of the population in developing economies is directly or indirectly dependent on the agricultural sector. Agriculture serves as a backbone for economic development by providing raw materials for the industrial sector, generating employment opportunities, absorbing the labor force, reducing poverty, meeting basic food needs, increasing foreign exchange reserves, and mitigating income inequality within and across countries. However, in many developing countries, outdated cultivation and harvesting methods are prevalent, with limited use of fertilizers and pesticides. This hinders sustainable agricultural production and the availability of cost-effective raw materials for manufacturing industries. Consequently, achieving sustainable per capita income, positive development outcomes, reduced income inequalities, and overall progress in developing countries becomes challenging (Oduola, 2017). Over the past five decades, income inequality has continued to rise in highly developed countries, particularly among members of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). The concepts of "inclusive growth" and "shared prosperity" aim to address income inequality and ensure the equitable distribution of economic benefits for growth in these developed countries. The significant increase in income inequality adversely affects people's living standards, making it challenging for low-income societies to prosper and participate equally in economic development processes. This leads to a disparity in living standards between low-income and middle-income individuals within OECD countries, hindering per capita economic growth and the equitable distribution of prosperity among different groups of people (Karagiannaki, 2017).

Financial inclusion is a critical aspect of a country's development, but it is important that funds are allocated transparently to developmental projects. The World Bank (2014) defines financial exclusion as the marginalization of individuals or populations from engaging with international institutional organizations due to cultural or religious reasons, resulting in their preference for underdevelopment rather than cooperating with these institutions for their own development. The success of Asian developing countries in overcoming economic barriers, achieving sustainable economic expansion, and promoting per capita economic growth has been linked to financial inclusion. It poses a significant challenge for policymakers and governments to develop Asian countries with the support of international financial institutions, focusing on improving sustainable economic expansion, expanding road infrastructure, and accessing funds from financial institutions for developmental projects. The expansion of economic growth helps reduce income inequality and alleviate poverty. Economic development and financial inclusion are interrelated, as international organizations provide a positive roadmap for poverty reduction and equal opportunities to address income inequality (Park & Mercado, 2015). In the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis, policymakers and stakeholders have increasingly focused on financial inclusion as a means to address the needs of the poor and underdeveloped groups and countries. Recognizing the importance of broad-based economic progress, international institutions such as the IMF, World Bank, and ADB have formulated policies and regulations to provide finance and offer productive guidance to developing countries worldwide. Financial inclusion encompasses access to financial services, low-interest loans, investment financing, savings opportunities, access to new technologies, and the utilization of natural resources, enabling all segments of the population in developing countries to contribute to economic progress and enhance labor productivity (Agyemang-Badu et al., 2018).

Income inequality is a pervasive issue that exists on a global scale, with the rich getting richer and the poor becoming poorer. This inequality stems from an unequal distribution of wealth and natural resources, which allows the rich to accumulate vast fortunes through the exploitation of the poor within nations. Such disparities can lead to societal unrest, as the disadvantaged population may resort to seeking their rightful share, causing disturbances in the social fabric (Freeman, 2018). Economists argue that income equality and social protection are closely intertwined. However, income inequality results in preferential treatment for those in higher positions in terms of legal privileges and wealth, while the lower-ranking individuals who work diligently struggle to earn fair wages. Injustice prevails as hardworking individuals do not receive adequate compensation, while those in positions of power, such as government officials, receive handsome salaries, travel insurance, and health insurance without deserving it. Such conditions contribute to societal breakdown, as a society cannot flourish when inequality persists among its members (Tekka et al., 2019). Social scientists assert that sustained economic development is contingent upon investing in human societies through the establishment of high-quality institutions. These institutions encompass political rights, robust defense structures, conducive civil work environments, and the protection of public and private property rights. Long-term economic progress can only be achieved when there is good governance, efficient public institutions, and a peaceful environment that attracts both local and foreign investors. Sustainable economic growth is fostered through democratic institutions, unfettered economic activities, ample civil and political rights, and the implementation of sound legal frameworks. These factors contribute to economic growth and serve as a means to eradicate extreme poverty and inequality while enabling the equitable distribution of wealth and natural resources, leading to prosperity for all (Coccia, 2021).

Good governance has emerged as a crucial instrument for promoting economic development, particularly in the 1990s. Developed nations have been at the forefront of promoting good governance and establishing robust public institutions that can freely execute policies and implementation. Good governance entails accountability, transparency, equal participation of the labor force, efficient utilization of human resources, equitable distribution of wealth, productive utilization of natural resources, equal wage rates, adherence to the rule of law, and timely and clear decision-making processes and responsibilities at all levels. Good governance plays a central role in achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), which include poverty reduction, hunger alleviation, environmental protection, and human development. Democracy and political stability are catalysts for promoting good governance. The objective of good governance is to provide a platform for managing law and order, revenue collection through taxes, and investment in productive resources such as infrastructure and the promotion of human well-being (Pal, 2017). Researchers and policymakers have extensively examined the relationship between governance, economic growth, and poverty reduction. Many scholars argue that good governance is the cornerstone of state development. However, there are differing opinions regarding the causation channels, and empirical evidence shows inconsistent results in terms of poverty eradication, economic growth, and governance. Efforts to promote and improve markets and address market failures facilitate investment and social transformation in the economy. While numerous studies and previous literature highlight a positive association between good governance and economic growth, some studies do not find a significant relationship in the case of Vietnam's economy (Nguyen et al., 2019).

The United Nations emphasizes that combating gender inequality is impossible without social protection for women across all aspects of life. Providing women with basic human rights is crucial for overcoming extreme poverty. Economic and social development poses significant challenges in developing societies. According to the Human Development Report, the estimated value of unpaid work performed by women annually amounts to \$11 trillion. Women's participation in various spheres of society, equal access to education, active involvement in businesses and decision-making processes, and the removal of barriers are all pivotal in breaking the cycle of poverty. Effective measures to reduce poverty and eradicate hunger globally cannot be achieved without ensuring women's equal rights, access to education, improved health, and greater access to land, employment, and financial resources (Ogu et al., 2016). Gender equality, economic development, and poverty reduction are fundamental goals for every society and political agenda. The United Nations has established 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to be achieved by 2030, aiming to improve living conditions worldwide. Key SDGs include SDG1 (end poverty everywhere), SDG5 (achieve gender equality and empower all girls and women), and SDG10 (reduce inequality within and among countries). In recent years, reliable efforts have been made towards achieving these goals with the participation of various stakeholders and political governments, particularly in the Asian subcontinent. These efforts have resulted in positive outcomes, including increased women's employment, reduced absolute poverty rates, and decreased global income inequality. However, OECD countries face challenges in addressing these issues due to social and cultural constraints (Nieuwenhuis et al., 2019). The following are the key research questions of the study, i.e.,

- I. Do government effectiveness, corruption control, and regulatory quality contribute to poverty reduction in a country?
- II. What role does female labor force involvement have in sustaining household economic activity and breaking the cycle of poverty?
- III. Do pro-rich federal policies emerge when there is a rise in income inequality, causing poverty rates to rise?

These research questions provide a starting point for studying the complex dynamics of poverty reduction, governance, gender, and income inequality. Conducting research on these topics can contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing poverty and inform policy interventions aimed at reducing poverty and promoting inclusive growth. For research, the following objectives are formed:

- I. To examine the role of good governance in reducing poverty incidence in a country.
- II. To analyze the role of an increasing share of women in the labor force in breaking the vicious cycle of poverty.
- III. To evaluate the effectiveness of pro-poor and pro-growth policies in a country.

By addressing these research objectives, the study aims to provide insights into the relationship between governance, female labor force participation, and poverty reduction. It also aims to assess the effectiveness of policy measures targeted at poverty alleviation and economic growth. The findings from this research can inform policymakers and stakeholders in developing strategies

and interventions for poverty reduction and inclusive development.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The existing literature extensively explores various channels and approaches for poverty reduction which is governance and poverty, Gender equality and poverty, Growth, inequality and poverty triangle and Governance, gender equality and poverty in Pakistan, providing valuable insights into the topic. However, a critical evaluation of the literature reveals certain gaps that need to be addressed in future studies. Jamil et al. (2021) conducted a study to explore the impact of good governance on poverty reduction, considering the involvement of both public and private stakeholders. The findings revealed that effective governance can contribute to a decrease in poverty and an increase in per capita income, as measured by GDP. The study emphasized the importance of consistent and reliable performance of government institutions, as exemplified by China's experience of higher per capita GDP corresponding to a decline in poverty rates. In contrast, countries in Sub-Saharan Africa continue to face high poverty rates, suggesting the need for sustainable policies and strategies to lift approximately 700 million people out of poverty between 1978 and 2012. Coccia (2021) analyzed the role of government institutions in implementing sustainable measures to reduce poverty and enhance economic growth in different countries. The study utilized data from 191 countries and examined the relationship between institutional factors, socio-economic factors, and different levels of development. The findings indicated that good governance and efficient institutions can help reduce income inequality and overcome poverty in diverse societies. Dossou et al. (2021) investigated the link between tourism and poverty alleviation, focusing on the effectiveness of government measures in economically disadvantaged regions of Latin American countries. The study utilized a panel of 15 Latin American countries spanning the period from 2003 to 2015. The researchers employed estimation techniques such as fixed effects (FE), Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE), and the generalized method of moments (GMM) model to obtain robust results. The findings demonstrated that the quality of governance plays a crucial role in poverty reduction, while ineffective and self-interested government spending on tourism can exacerbate poverty levels. Furthermore, the study highlighted the complementary impact of macroeconomic variables such as the quality of governance and tourism on poverty reduction. Wu and Christensen (2021) examined the corruption rates in different regions of China, specifically focusing on poverty causes in villages and towns. The study drew on literature reviews, government websites, interviews, and newspaper sources. The findings indicated that misappropriation of poverty alleviation funds due to corruption contributes to poverty in the country. Moreover, the study revealed that corruption rates are higher in villages compared to towns, and corruption tends to be more prevalent at the individual level rather than among groups of people. The results suggest the importance of implementing transparent accountability measures and adopting cultural and instrumental approaches to mitigate corruption in villages and towns. The study proposed the need for a better rule of law and new anti-corruption policies to improve accountability among individuals and groups, which in turn can contribute to reducing poverty.

Woodward (2021) argued that it is the responsibility of the state to focus on primary institutions within the child social welfare system to promote gender equality and reduce poverty. The study emphasized the equal importance of men and women in the efforts to alleviate poverty, highlighting that gender equality is essential for poverty reduction. The author emphasized the role of state-led paternalism, which entails reforming "bad" parents into "good" parents and ensuring equal opportunities for all family members, regardless of gender. By collaborating with the state, this approach aims to reduce poverty in the United States by addressing gender discrimination and promoting equal development opportunities for all. Ronaghi (2023) investigated the impact of governance on poverty and unemployment rates before and after the Covid-19 pandemic in the United States. The study also examined the influence of neighboring states' conditions using panel data from 2011 to 2020, encompassing 49 states in America. The empirical analysis employed spatial econometric techniques for panel data. The results indicated that during the Covid-19 pandemic, governance exhibited negative performance, and a high income inequality rate contributed to poverty. Furthermore, the study found that negative governance performance, increased unemployment, lower wage rates, increased hunger and food insecurity, reduced health insurance coverage, and higher population growth rates were factors affecting poverty during the pandemic. The study concluded that governance played a crucial role in controlling poverty during the Covid-19 outbreak in the United States. Nguyen et al. (2019) investigated the impact of the quality of good governance and public administration on economic growth and poverty reduction using provincial-level data collected from citizens' experiences in Vietnam. The quality of good governance and public administration was measured using the Vietnam Governance and Public Administration Performance Index (PAPI) survey. Through province fixed-effect regression analysis, the study found an indirect relationship between good governance, public administration, and per capita income in the country. The results also indicated that good governance and improved public administration contributed to a reduction in income inequality and poverty. The study suggested that excellent governance and effective public administration were beneficial for the poorest individuals across provinces in Vietnam.

Dossou et al. (2021) conducted a study to explore the correlation between tourism, governance quality, and poverty reduction in Latin American countries. The researchers utilized a fixed-effect estimation approach and a panel of 15 Latin American countries, *Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory*, 2(1), 132-149 (2023)

using secondary data from 2003 to 2015. To ensure robust analysis, they employed two econometric techniques: the generalized method of moments (GMM) model and the Panel Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) model estimation. The results revealed that the quality of good governance played a significant role in poverty reduction, while tourism had a negative impact on poverty. An interesting finding of this study was that the improvement of governance quality, along with the development of tourism, supported poverty alleviation in Latin America. Zerbian and Romero (2021) investigated the role of cities in promoting good governance for food security, focusing on the outcomes of Madrid's urban food plan. The study highlighted that during times of food insecurity, good governance played a complementary role in addressing the challenges of food insecurity. Moreover, the results indicated that with good governance, new urban initiatives could create comprehensive and autonomous solutions for food security. Furthermore, good governance was found to be crucial in identifying critical problems, addressing societal challenges, and overcoming obstacles to effective governance. Cassimon et al. (2023) examined the impact of food aid and governance quality on both food security and malnutrition in 25 sub-Saharan African countries. The study utilized secondary data from 1996 to 2018 and employed various measures for food and nutrition security, such as average production value, average unit energy supply, and the prevalence of malnutrition. The empirical analysis using the generalized method of moments (GMM) estimator demonstrated a strong association between food aid, governance quality, food security, and malnutrition security. The results indicated that governance indicators, particularly control of corruption and political stability, increased food aid and nutrition security while reducing undernourishment across the sub-Saharan Africa region. The findings suggested that the quality of governance, including effective control of corruption and political stability, significantly promoted food aid and sustainable nutrition security in sub-Saharan Africa.

Zang et al. (2023) conducted a multidimensional analysis to explore the relationship between political corruption and national poverty across the globe. The study utilized panel data from 117 countries spanning the years 1992 to 2017. The results revealed a significant direct relationship between national corruption and poverty. Additionally, the findings indicated that national corruption contributed to national poverty by exacerbating inequality at all levels worldwide. Furthermore, the existence of haven halo hypotheses, foreign direct investment, and public services weakened the relationship between national corruption and national poverty, underscoring the fact that international bilateral relationships and societies often fail to provide equal rights to the poor and poorest individuals globally. Song et al. (2022) examined the impact of fiscal decentralization on economic growth and poverty alleviation using panel data from the northwestern and northeastern regions of 24 provinces over the period from 2010 to 2018. The study employed the Moran's I index to determine the degree of poverty in developed areas, while the spatial Durbin model was used to assess the effects of fiscal decentralization and economic development on poverty alleviation. The results revealed that fiscal revenue decentralization and high economic growth had a significant impact on poverty alleviation. Moreover, fiscal expenditure decentralization was found to be an effective measure for reducing poverty across the region. The empirical findings also highlighted that economic growth and fiscal decentralization promoted good governance and reduced poverty. Additionally, government expenditure on structural infrastructure and human capital was found to stimulate economic growth across all sectors. Zhao et al. (2022) conducted a study to investigate the impact of fiscal tariff revenue on poverty alleviation without environmental degradation in China. They analyzed data from 2010 to 2019, focusing on a panel of 281 prefecture-level cities. The researchers employed fixed-effect and spatial Durbin models to derive empirical findings. Their study revealed a positive effect of fiscal decentralization on green poverty alleviation. Moreover, the implementation of clean and green environmental policies demonstrated a significantly positive impact on poverty reduction. On the other hand, informal environmental regulatory policies were found to exacerbate poverty and harm the environment. The results highlighted the importance of effective environmental regulatory policies and an optimal fiscal decentralization structure in promoting green poverty alleviation and preserving a sustainable environment globally. Lechman and Popowska (2022) examined the use of digital technology as a means to eradicate poverty in low-income and lower-middle-income countries. Their study utilized data from the World Telecommunication/ICT Indicators Database (2020) and the World Bank Development Indicators (2021) for a sample of 40 developing countries. To analyze the results, the researchers employed various statistical models, including panel regression, logistic growth, time trend analysis, and locally weighted polynomial estimation. The findings indicated that well-organized ICT institutions had a significant impact on poverty eradication in developing countries. These institutions facilitated increased employment, school enrollment, and the integration of digital technology into other sectors. The study emphasized the crucial roles played by local and national governments, as well as stakeholders, in providing sustainable opportunities in the IT industry for the younger generation, thereby contributing to the achievement of development goals. Atkins et al. (2022) explored the importance of social protection in alleviating poverty in African countries. The study highlighted that protecting basic human rights can reduce poverty and foster sustainable growth. Social protection programs were found to promote well-being and empower women and girls. The findings underscored the significance of gender equality, addressing external shocks (climate events, natural disasters, pandemics, wars, conflicts, displacement), and strengthening core programs and services to achieve sustainable development across

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regions and countries. Based on the literature, it is assumed that promoting a higher female-to-male ratio in economic activities can lead to poverty reduction.

Oktay and Algan (2022) investigated the major causes of global poverty, particularly in developing and low-income countries. The study aimed to estimate the relationship between income inequality, economic growth, and poverty across different regions and countries. The researchers categorized countries into different income groups and employed a cross-sectional technique for estimation. The results indicated that income inequality contributes to poverty and hinders economic development. Overcoming income inequality and poverty is crucial for the development process. The findings also showed that a decrease in economic growth across all income groups leads to poverty and income inequality, while an increase in income inequalities among middle-income groups promotes economic growth. High-income countries, on the other hand, experience increased economic growth and reduced income inequality. Aghaei and Lawell (2022) examined the relationship between energy consumption, economic growth, income inequality, and poverty in Iran. They used instrumental variables and simultaneous equations models to address endogeneity issues and improve efficiency in their estimations. The results showed that a fair income distribution in Iran can enhance economic growth, reduce poverty, and improve energy access. Interestingly, the study found that higher energy consumption leads to increased GDP but also contributes to income inequality. The findings suggest that policies aimed at improving energy access can help increase GDP, reduce income inequality, and alleviate poverty. Ferreira et al. (2022) investigated the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals by 2030 and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on these goals. According to a World Bank report, the pandemic and the Ukraine war led to an additional 95 million people falling into extreme poverty in 2022. This has exacerbated issues of income inequality, low GDP per capita, and poverty, especially in developing countries. The study emphasizes the need for policy-makers to develop sustainable platforms and address the increasing frequency of natural disasters caused by climate change. It highlights the responsibility of policy-makers to overcome these critical global situations. Suparman (2022) studied the relationship between economic growth, income inequality, and poverty in the provinces of Indonesia using panel data. The study utilized data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) on Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) at Constant Prices, the number of poor populations, and the Gini ratio from 2015 to 2020. The panel data regression models used were the Common Effect Model (CEM), Fixed Effect Model (FEM), and Random Effect Model (REM). The results consistently showed that economic growth (LOGPDRB) and income inequality (GIN) have a positive effect on the number of poor people. When these variables increase, there is an increase in the number of poor people across the provinces in Indonesia. Zang et al. (2023) investigated the multidimensional analysis of how political corruption exacerbates national poverty worldwide. The study utilized panel data from 117 countries from 1992 to 2017. The results showed a significant direct relationship between national corruption and poverty. National corruption was found to promote national poverty through increased inequality at all levels across the globe. The study also confirmed the "haven hollow hypothesis," which suggests that foreign direct investment and public services mitigate the relationship between national corruption and national poverty. The findings indicated that international bilateral relationships and societies do not provide equal rights to the poor and the poorest globally. Song et al. (2022) analyzed the impact of fiscal decentralization on economic growth and poverty alleviation. The study utilized panel data from 24 provinces in the northwestern and northeastern parts of a country during the time period from 2010 to 2018. Poverty levels in developed areas were determined based on the effects of fiscal decentralization, economic development, and poverty eradication, using the Moral index and spatial Durbin Model. The results showed that fiscal revenue decentralization and high economic growth had a significant impact on poverty alleviation. Additionally, fiscal expenditure decentralization was found to be an effective measure in reducing poverty across the region. The empirical findings also demonstrated that the rate of economic growth and fiscal decentralization promoted good governance and reduced poverty. Government expenditure on structural infrastructure and human capital was found to promote economic growth in all sectors.

Zhao et al. (2022) examined the effect of fiscal tariff revenue on poverty alleviation without environmental degradation in 281 prefecture-level cities in China. The study utilized time period data from 2010 to 2019 and employed fixed effect models and spatial Durbin Models for empirical findings. The study found that fiscal decentralization had a positive effect on green poverty alleviation. Clean and green environmental policies had a significantly positive effect on poverty reduction, while informal environmental regulatory policies enhanced poverty and were harmful to the environment. The results indicated that effective environmental regulatory policies and an optimal fiscal decentralization structure improve green poverty alleviation and promote efforts for preserving a sustainable environment globally. Arif et al. (2023) conducted an empirical analysis using the environmental Kuznets curve framework, which focuses on the relationship between income inequality and per capita income in Pakistan. The study utilized the econometric technique nonlinear autoregressive distributed lags model (NARDL) and a time series dataset covering the period from 1981 to 2021. Explanatory variables included income, employment, government spending, and corruption, while the Gini coefficient was used as the dependent variable. The results showed that the coefficients of all explanatory variables, except income, were positively correlated with inequality in both the long run and short run. Additionally, macroeconomic

variables such as economic growth were found to decrease income inequality in Pakistan. The findings suggested that access to financial resources, job-oriented policies, and effective anti-corruption measures could reduce income inequality in the country.

Shah (2023) explored the relationship between good governance, tourism expansion, and poverty alleviation in SAARC countries using a panel dataset from 2009 to 2019. The study employed the econometric techniques of fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) and dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) for empirical analysis. The results indicated that effective government measures for tourism development contributed to international tourism and helped in poverty reduction. The study also revealed an interconnectedness between effective government measures for tourism development and poverty eradication in the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) countries. Based on the cited literature, the following are the research hypotheses of the study, i.e.,

H1: The effectiveness of government mitigates the poverty cycle.

H2: Weak institutions foster corruption and trap their population in poverty.

H3: Poverty can be reduced by regulating institutional quality.

H4: The higher female share in labor force participation rate tends to decrease poverty in a country.

H5: Rising income inequality is likely to increase poverty incidence.

This study emphasizes the critical role of improving governance quality in tackling gender inequality, increasing income levels, promoting economic growth, and alleviating poverty in Pakistan. The findings highlight the need to address governance issues at all levels of society to achieve sustainable development and poverty reduction in the country. The study's insights can inform policymakers and stakeholders in formulating strategies and policies to improve governance and effectively address poverty-related challenges in Pakistan.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study employed robust regression analysis, as depicted in equation (1), to examine the relationships among the variables under investigation. Prior to conducting the robust regression analysis, leverage plots were examined to assess the extent to which variables deviated from their true regression line.

$$POV = \alpha + \beta_1RQ + \beta_2CC + \beta_3FLFPR + \beta_4INEQ + \beta_5UNEMP + \beta_6GDPPC + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where:

POV represents the poverty headcount ratio,

RQ represents regulatory quality,

CC represents control of corruption,

FLFPR represents female labor force participation rate,

INEQ represents income inequality,

UNEMP represents the unemployment rate,

GDPPC represents GDP per capita, and

ε represents the stochastic random term.

The data will be collected from the World Governance Indicators (WGI) and World Development Indicators (WDI) published by the World Bank (2022). The explanatory variables include regulatory, control of corruption, female labor force participation rate, income inequality quality, unemployment rate, GDP per capita, and the dependent variable is Poverty. In this chapter, we describe the data source and nature of the data, and variables, and also describe the methods used for the analysis of the data. All of the variables used for the analysis were covered in this section. The type of variable, the rationale for selecting it, and the projected sign of the variable were all also covered. List of variables shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Variables

Variables	Units	Definition
Poverty head ratio count rate	Percentage of total population below the national poverty line	Poverty head ratio is a measure use to evaluate the proportion of population living below the poverty line
Regulatory Quality	-2.5 to 2.5	Refers to effectiveness, transparency and consistency of country regulatory framework and institutions

Variables	Units	Definition
Control of Corruption	-2.5 to 2.5	Refers to the extent to which a country institutions governance mechanisms effectively prevent corruption
Government effectiveness	-2.5 to 2.5	Refers to capability and efficiency of a government and fulfilling its responsibility to its citizens
Female Labor Force Participation Rate	Percentage of female Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24.	Refers to percentage of women actively engage in labor market
Income Inequality	Gini index	Refers to unequal distribution of income within particular society or economy
Unemployment Rate	Percentage of male labor force ages 15-24	Percentage of unemployed individual in the labor market
GDP Per Capita	Constant US\$ in 2015	Average economic output per person in given country

Source: World Bank (2022).

Ordinary least squares estimators are sensitive to the presence of observations that lie outside the norm for the regression model of interest. The sensitivity of conventional regression methods to these outlier observations can result in coefficient estimates that do not accurately reflect the underlying statistical relationship. Robust least squares refer to a variety of regression methods designed to be robust, or less sensitive, to outliers. EViews offers three different methods for robust least squares: M-estimation (Huber, 1973), S-estimation (Rousseeuw and Yohai, 1984), and MM-estimation (Yohai 1987). The three methods differ in their emphases: 1) M-estimation addresses dependent variable outliers where the value of the dependent variable differs markedly from the regression model norm (large residuals), 2) S-estimation is a computationally intensive procedure that focuses on outliers in the regressor variables (high leverages), and 3) MM-estimation is a combination of S-estimation and M-estimation. The procedure starts by performing S-estimation, and then uses the estimates obtained from S-estimation as the starting point for M-estimation. Since MM-estimation is a combination of the other two methods, it addresses outliers in both the dependent and independent variables. The robust regression statistical technique allows for the identification of outliers and the minimization of residual sizes and high leverages across the entire dataset.

Granger Causality is an econometric concept developed by Clive Granger in the 1960s, commonly used to determine the causal relationship between two-time series variables data set. The Granger causality test examines whether one variable, X, can better predict the values of another variable, Y, when incorporating lagged values of X in the prediction. If the inclusion of lagged values of X improves the prediction of Y, it implies that X has a causal influence on Y. Variance Decomposition Analysis (VDA) is a statistical technique that partitions the total variance in an outcome variable, such as firm financial performance, into various components based on factors such as firm, industry, and country. VDA provides researchers with a roadmap and better insights into their research area. It also aids in guiding researchers and policymakers by providing predictions and insights for further analysis. Therefore, Variance Decomposition Analysis is widely used in the social sciences and strategic planning in administration.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables. The poverty incidence has a mean value of 42.592 percent, with a maximum value of 64.3 and a minimum value of 21.9. This suggests that approximately 50 percent of the population is living below the poverty line. The standard deviation of 17.076 indicates a wide dispersion in the poverty data, meaning that the variable can vary significantly. The poverty incidence variable exhibits a positively skewed distribution with a high kurtosis value. This indicates that there is a concentration of data towards the lower end of the poverty incidence scale, with a few extreme values on the higher end.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	POV	CC	GEF	RQ	FLFPR	INEQ	GDPPC	UNEMP
Mean	42.59259	-0.946038	-0.601734	-0.673829	17.47711	30.16667	1164.227	3.797889
Median	44.10000	-0.894910	-0.597105	-0.648276	18.47000	29.70000	1149.851	1.368000
Maximum	64.30000	-0.777167	-0.380625	-0.479762	22.45400	33.10000	1473.865	10.81200
Minimum	21.90000	-1.220030	-0.829370	-1.049112	10.36800	28.70000	931.7068	0.901000
Std. Dev.	17.07643	0.145622	0.134490	0.120431	3.242001	1.372533	186.5391	3.524451
Skewness	0.123592	-0.483416	-0.115204	-1.045179	-0.504936	0.955799	0.323165	0.871425
Kurtosis	1.459052	1.865385	1.876154	4.872267	2.326185	2.908392	1.838109	2.181219

Source: Author's estimate.

The governance indicators, including control of corruption, government effectiveness, and regulatory control, show mean values that suggest a high level of corruption, minimal government effectiveness, and inadequate regulatory qualities in the country. The female labor force participation rate has a mean value of 17.477 percent, indicating that there is room for improvement in terms of female participation in the labor force. Increasing female labor force participation can support economic activities and contribute to poverty reduction. Income inequality, represented by the variable "inequality," has a maximum value of 33.10 and a minimum value of 28.70, with a mean value of 30.16. This suggests that the country experiences more than 30 percent income inequality based on the available data. The per capita income variable has a maximum value of \$1473, with a mean value of \$1164. This indicates the average income per person in the country. The unemployment rate variable has a maximum value of 10.812, with a mean value of 3.797. This suggests that unemployment can have an influence on economic activities and may contribute to an increase in poverty incidence in the country.

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix, which examines the relationships between variables. The correlation between control of corruption and poverty incidence is negative, indicating that higher levels of corruption are associated with lower poverty incidence in the country. This suggests that corruption may not be a significant factor contributing to poverty incidence.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	POV	CC	GEF	RQ	FLFPR	INEQ	GDPPC	UNEMP
POV	1							

CC	-0.535965	1						
	0.0040	-----						
GEF	0.269759	0.271918	1					
	0.1736	0.1700	-----					
RQ	-0.083001	-0.028292	-0.128887	1				
	0.6806	0.8886	0.5217	-----				
FLFPR	-0.918434	0.440555	-0.293616	0.046719	1			
	0.0000	0.0215	0.1372	0.8170	-----			
INEQ	0.134206	0.002771	0.346545	0.022422	-0.271732	1		
	0.5045	0.9891	0.0766	0.9116	0.1703	-----		
GDPPC	-0.960944	0.632568	-0.076367	0.074453	0.870611	-0.141776	1.000000	

Variables	POV	CC	GEF	RQ	FLFPR	INEQ	GDPPC	UNEMP
	0.0000	0.0004	0.7050	0.7121	0.0000	0.4806	-----	
UNEMP	-0.834190	0.567814	0.049707	-0.064189	0.706247	-0.103563	0.903752	1.000000
	0.0000	0.0020	0.8055	0.7504	0.0000	0.6072	0.0000	-----

Source: Author's estimate.

The correlation between female labor force participation rate (FLFPR) and poverty incidence is negative, indicating that an increase in female labor force participation is associated with a decrease in poverty incidence. This suggests that promoting female participation in the labor force can have a positive impact on poverty reduction. Economic growth has a negative correlation with poverty incidence. This means that as economic growth increases, poverty incidence tends to decrease. This highlights the importance of sustained economic growth for poverty reduction efforts. The correlation between unemployment and poverty incidence is negative, suggesting that higher levels of unemployment are associated with lower poverty incidence. This implies that unemployed individuals may be more likely to escape poverty, potentially through finding employment opportunities. Overall, the correlation matrix provides insights into the relationships between variables. It indicates that control of corruption, female labor force participation, economic growth, and unemployment are factors that have varying associations with poverty incidence in the country. Figure 1 displays the Influence Statistics, which includes four measures: RStudent, Hat matrix, DFFITS, and COVRATIO.

Influence Statistics

Figure 1: Influence Statistics

Source: Author's estimate.

The R-Student statistic identifies two outliers in the model. These outliers have a notable influence on the regression results, indicating that their inclusion significantly affects the estimated coefficients. The Hat matrix identifies one outlier in the model. This outlier has a high leverage, meaning that it has a substantial impact on the fitted values of the regression equation. The DFFITS statistic highlights three outliers. DFFITS measures the change in the fitted values when each observation is removed from the model. These outliers have a considerable influence on the overall fit of the regression model. The COVRATIO statistic identifies four outliers. COVRATIO assesses the effect of deleting each observation on the covariance matrix of the estimated coefficients. These outliers have a substantial impact on the precision and stability of the estimated coefficients. The

presence of potential outliers in the model suggests that further investigation and estimation are necessary. These outliers can significantly affect the regression results and may need to be addressed to ensure the robustness and validity of the findings. Figure 2 can provide additional insights for the estimation process.

Figure 2: Leverage Plots
Source: Author's estimate.

Figure 2 illustrates the leverage plot, which displays the standard deviation of the leverage values for each regressor. The wide standard deviation observed in the plot indicates the presence of potential outliers in each of the regressors. The leverage values represent the influence that each observation has on the fitted values of the regression equation. High leverage points have the potential to significantly affect the estimated coefficients and overall model fit. Given the wide spread of the standard deviation in the leverage plot, it is evident that there are potential outliers present in the dataset. To account for the influence of these outliers and ensure more robust regression results, the study has decided to employ robust least square regression. Robust regression techniques are specifically designed to handle outliers and leverage points effectively. By using robust regression, the study aims to obtain more reliable and accurate estimates by mitigating the impact of these potential outliers on the regression model. This approach will enhance the robustness of the analysis and provide more robust and trustworthy insights into the relationship between the variables under investigation. The robust least square regression results in Table 4 provide valuable insights into the relationship between various factors and poverty incidence.

Table 4: Robust Least Square Estimates

Variables	RLS 1	RLS 2
CC	-1.659 (0.512)	-----
GEF	25.707 (0.000)	24.906 (0.000)
RQ	2.050 (0.366)	3.275 (0.068)

Variables	RLS 1	RLS 2
FLFPR	-1.190 (0.000)	-0.921 (0.000)
GDPPC	-0.070 (0.000)	-0.084 (0.000)
INEQ	-1.128 (0.000)	-0.943 (0.000)
UNEMP	0.141 (0.475)	0.762 (0.000)
C	194.268 (0.000)	199.713 (0.000)
Robust Statistics		
R ²	0.802	0.705
ADJ R ²	0.788	0.688
RW ²	0.986	0.992

Source: Author's estimate. Note: Small bracket shows probability value.

Government effectiveness shows a positive relationship with poverty incidence, suggesting that the current level of government effectiveness is not sufficient to effectively reduce poverty in the country. This highlights the need for improved governance and policy implementation to address poverty issues. Government regulatory quality shows a positive relationship with poverty incidence, suggesting that the government regulatory quality is insufficient to reduce poverty in the country. This highlights the need for improved governance quality to address poverty issues. Female labor force participation rate (FLFPR) exhibits a negative relationship with poverty incidence, indicating that increasing women's participation in the labor market can help break the cycle of poverty. Encouraging more women to enter the workforce can contribute to poverty reduction efforts. Income inequality shows a negative relationship with poverty incidence in this analysis. While it is commonly believed that inequality exacerbates poverty, the presence of a higher FLFPR appears to offset the negative impact of inequality on poverty. This underscores the importance of promoting gender equality and women's economic empowerment as a means to alleviate poverty. Economic growth demonstrates a negative relationship with poverty incidence, suggesting that economic activities and growth can contribute to reducing poverty. A thriving economy provides opportunities for income generation and employment, which can help lift people out of poverty. There is a positive relationship between unemployment and poverty in a country. The results argue that higher unemployment leads to increase to poverty gap between rich and poor

The findings from Ochi et al. (2023) support the negative relationship between governance quality and poverty incidence, with governance reaching a threshold level that leads to a decrease in poverty. Similarly, Ronaghi & Scorsone (2023) find a negative correlation between governance index and poverty, while income inequality is positively related to poverty incidence. These studies highlight the importance of good governance in poverty reduction efforts. Rulinawaty et al. (2023) emphasize the role of government participation, information-based policies, stakeholder collaboration, and effective legislation in poverty alleviation. Puspitasari (2023) stresses the need for improved governance through effective legislation and bureaucratic reforms to reduce poverty. Malaj (2023) finds a negative relationship between corruption and poverty, suggesting that lower corruption levels contribute to economic growth and reduced poverty. Higher corruption rates are associated with increased economic, financial, and social inequality, leading to a larger population living above the poverty line. Paul (2023) highlights the impact of women's labor force participation during recession periods in reducing family poverty levels. Choi & Nam (2023) discuss the gender disparity effect on childhood poverty and unemployment, emphasizing the importance of equal opportunities and reducing inequality to minimize poverty incidence. Kanjere (2023) highlights that limited opportunities for women hinder their skill development. Various forms of gender disparities, such as restricted access to economic opportunities and labor market resources, contribute to poverty incidence. The study suggests that addressing gender disparities can help reduce poverty, and empowering women financially enables their active participation in economic activities alongside men, leading to overall benefits for the country. Oyewunmi & Obayelu (2023) argue that poverty incidence is higher among women-led farming households and men-led farming households in rural areas compared to non-farming households. Gender-blind programs are inadequate in reducing poverty, and bridging the gender gap is crucial to achieving the first Sustainable Development Goal (SDG1) of poverty alleviation. Fosu (2023) finds that inequality and economic growth are complementary factors for development, although in some cases, inequality can be the primary driver of poverty change. Income equality and economic

growth exhibit a positive relationship, and beyond a certain point, inequality decreases, contributing to poverty reduction. When income is equally distributed, individuals can break the cycle of poverty. Asongu & Kousar et al. (2023) argue that both traditional economic growth (GDP) and green economic growth (GGDP) have a negative impact on poverty reduction and income inequality. The study suggests that effective policies and their implementation for green economic growth, which promotes environmental preservation, can minimize health expenditures and redirect resources towards poverty elimination and reducing income inequality. Velkovska & Trenovski (2023) find that sustainable economic growth and social expenditures contribute to poverty reduction. Economic growth plays a vital role in poverty reduction, while social expenditures are also important, although they have a lesser impact on economic growth. Income inequality promotes economic growth, but social expenditures are effective in reducing poverty alongside less robust economic growth. Asongu (2023) concludes that income inequality unconditionally promotes poverty incidence and related factors. Financial institutions play a significant role in promoting access to finance, which can help overcome income inequality and lead to poverty reduction. Inefficient and minimal levels of financial institutions have unfavorable effects on income inequality and poverty challenges. Olaoye (2023) investigates the impact of sustained economic growth on poverty reduction, particularly in resource-rich countries. The study finds that income inequality negatively affects economic growth and poverty incidence. Additionally, poverty has adverse effects on other developmental sectors over time. Resource-rich economies should diversify beyond a single highly developed sector to overcome these challenges and promote sustainable development.

Karahasan (2023) finds that economic growth has a direct impact on poverty reduction. However, sustainable economic growth occurs when countries focus on industrialization and job creation. Manufacturing employment plays a significant role in poverty alleviation, accounting for nearly 50 percent of poverty reduction. Houria (2023) argues that there is a positive and strong correlation between economic freedom and human capital. This implies that economic freedom and human capital have a complementary relationship with economic growth. Economic freedom attracts foreign direct investment, and the presence of well-qualified and skilled human capital further attracts investment, leading to economic growth. Zhou et al. (2023) investigate the role of road infrastructure in economic development. The study finds that the construction of road infrastructure is a complementary factor for economic development. Developing road infrastructure enhances rural development, leading to industrialization and the creation of more job opportunities. This, in turn, increases per capita income and promotes aggregate economic growth, ultimately contributing to poverty alleviation in impoverished areas of the country. The R-squared value indicates that approximately 78.8(68.8) % of the variation in poverty incidence can be explained by the independent variables included in the regression model. This suggests that the model has a reasonably good fit in explaining the factors influencing poverty incidence. Table 5 presents the Granger causality estimates, indicating the causal relationships between variables.

Table 5: Granger Causality Estimates

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
POV ≠RQ		3.74958	0.0414
FLFPR ≠POV	25	4.70647	0.0211
POV ≠UNEMP		5.12994	0.0159
UNEMP ≠CC	25	3.01224	0.0719
INEQ ≠FLFPR	25	6.42675	0.0070
FLFPR ≠GDPPC		2.79612	0.0850

Source: Author's estimate.

The findings are as follows: Poverty (POV) Granger causes regulatory quality implies that higher levels of poverty increase the need for regulatory measures in a country, which can help improve economic activities and overall governance. Female labor force participation rate (FLFPR) has a unidirectional relationship with poverty: This finding confirms that as the female labor force participation rate increases, the likelihood of reducing poverty also increases. Higher female participation in the labor market contributes to poverty reduction efforts. Poverty has a unidirectional relationship with unemployment, which suggest that higher levels of poverty lead to an increase in unemployment rates within a country. Poverty can create unfavorable conditions for job opportunities and result in higher unemployment rates. Unemployment causes corruption reveals a unidirectional relationship between unemployment and corruption. This suggests that higher levels of unemployment may increase the likelihood of individuals engaging in corrupt practices as a means of survival or income generation. Inequality has a unidirectional relationship with female labor force participation rate. The findings indicate that higher levels of income inequality lead to increased female participation in the labor force. Inequality may push more women to seek employment opportunities to sustain their livelihoods and bridge the income gap. Female labor force participation rate causes economic growth. The results suggest that an increase in female labor force participation leads to higher economic growth. Greater female participation in the labor force generates more economic activities, contributing to overall economic development. These

findings highlight the interrelationships between poverty, regulatory quality, unemployment, corruption, inequality, female labor force participation, and economic growth. Understanding these causal links can inform policy and decision-making processes aimed at reducing poverty, improving governance, and promoting inclusive economic development.

Table 6 presents the Impulse Response Function (IRF) analysis, which provides insights into the dynamic relationship between governance indicators (control of corruption, government effectiveness, regulatory quality) and poverty reduction over a ten-year period.

Table 6: Impulse Response Function

Period	POV	CC	GEF	RQ	FLFPR	INEQ	GDPPC	UNEMP
1	2.175840	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.392794	-1.846740	0.391014	-0.736246	-0.271917	1.204762	-0.821697	-0.001699
3	0.264986	-0.899200	0.203234	-0.136489	-0.706691	0.330580	-0.057543	0.007254
4	1.251446	-1.381746	-0.229458	-0.044695	-2.050280	0.952639	0.043425	0.066317
5	0.191318	-1.998784	-0.203502	0.125388	-2.439708	1.074101	-0.122239	0.059158
6	-0.327699	-0.263005	-0.217070	0.285080	-2.341295	0.488779	0.051075	0.088261
7	0.136118	-0.272094	-0.350968	0.078329	-2.174755	0.688878	0.035899	0.098715
8	-0.093659	-0.523053	-0.295784	-0.318165	-2.246148	0.668152	-0.149398	0.068934
9	-0.117354	-0.027239	-0.598076	-0.039505	-2.056582	0.649767	-0.007404	0.072668
10	0.086219	-0.242137	-0.683148	0.201164	-1.981831	0.794291	-0.057305	0.064134

Source: Author's estimate.

The findings suggest the following, i.e., control of corruption (CC), government effectiveness (GEF), and regulatory quality (RQ) have a favorable impact on poverty reduction: This implies that improvements in controlling corruption, enhancing government effectiveness, and ensuring regulatory quality can contribute to poverty reduction efforts. Other socio-economic factors are also expected to play a role in poverty reduction: The analysis suggests that factors not specifically related to governance indicators may also influence poverty reduction over the next ten years. These factors could include variables such as economic growth, income inequality, unemployment, and female labor force participation rate, among others. The IRF analysis indicates that changes in these factors are expected to have an impact on poverty incidence. Table 7 presents the Variance Decomposition Analysis, which provides insights into the contribution of different variables to the variance of poverty reduction over a ten-year period.

Table 7: Variance Decomposition Analysis

Period	S.E.	POV	CC	GEF	RQ	FLFPR	INEQ	GDPPC	UNEMP
1	2.175840	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	3.345825	43.66918	30.46528	1.365774	4.842158	0.660488	12.96570	6.031387	2.58E-05
3	3.570058	38.90672	33.10245	1.523666	4.399160	4.498518	12.24555	5.323505	0.000435
4	4.625230	30.50051	28.64630	1.153881	2.630256	22.32999	11.53781	3.180437	0.020817
5	5.710161	20.12364	31.04762	0.884072	1.773930	32.90559	11.10825	2.132511	0.024391
6	6.216257	17.25820	26.37695	0.867917	1.707158	41.95150	9.991377	1.806161	0.040741
7	6.639192	15.17148	23.29137	1.040312	1.510503	47.50665	9.835564	1.586299	0.057823
8	7.075919	13.37402	21.05142	1.090594	1.531981	51.89992	9.550558	1.441107	0.060396
9	7.422901	12.17790	19.13068	1.640198	1.394937	54.83740	9.444794	1.309627	0.064465
10	7.761355	11.15130	17.59590	2.275005	1.343107	56.67918	9.686356	1.203349	0.065794

Source: Author's estimate.

The findings indicate the following: Female labor force participation rate has the greatest impact on poverty reduction: According to the analysis, female labor force participation rate has the highest standard variance shock of 56.679 percent on poverty reduction. This suggests that increasing female labor force participation can be a significant factor in decreasing poverty levels across the country. Gender equality and empowering women to participate in the labor market can have a substantial impact on poverty reduction efforts. Other factors also contribute to poverty reduction: The analysis considers the contribution of various factors, including control of corruption, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, and potentially other socio-economic variables. While female labor force participation rate has the greatest impact, it is important to note that other factors also play a role in poverty reduction, although to a lesser extent. Regulatory quality has a relatively lower impact on poverty

reduction: The analysis suggests that regulatory quality has a lower standard variance shock compared to female labor force participation rate. This implies that regulatory quality, while still important, may have a comparatively smaller influence on poverty reduction over the next ten years.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to explore the role of good governance, the increased participation of women in the labor market, and the evaluation of pro-poor and pro-growth public policies in breaking the cycle of poverty within a country. The empirical analysis employs the robust regression statistical technique and utilizes a time series dataset covering the period from 1996 to 2022. The findings of the study reveal important associations between various factors and poverty incidence within the country. Firstly, the results indicate a significantly positive relationship between government effectiveness (GEF) and poverty incidence. This suggests that higher levels of government effectiveness are associated with increased poverty rates, indicating that the current state of governance may not be sufficient in effectively reducing poverty. Further government regulatory quality, unemployment and poverty both have a positive relationship between them. On the other hand, the study finds that the female labor force participation rate (FLFPR), income equality (INEQ), and Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) have a reducing effect on poverty incidence. This implies that higher levels of female labor force participation, greater income equality, and increased per capita income contribute to a decrease in poverty within the country. To examine the causal relationships between the variables, the study employs the Granger Causality econometric technique. The results of the Granger Causality analysis indicate a unidirectional relationship between poverty and regulatory quality, as well as poverty and unemployment. Additionally, there is a unidirectional relationship between female labor force participation rate and both poverty and GDP per capita. Furthermore, the unemployment rate exhibits a unidirectional relationship with corruption. In terms of variance decomposition analysis, the study finds that the female labor force participation rate has the potential to increase poverty within the country. This suggests that while increasing female labor force participation is important, there may be other factors or limitations that counteract its positive impact on poverty reduction. Lastly, the Impulse Response Function analysis reveals that the governance indicators, including control of corruption, regulatory quality, and government effectiveness, are likely to contribute to an increase in poverty incidence. This can be attributed to higher levels of corruption, inadequate regulatory quality, and insufficient government effectiveness, which hinder effective poverty reduction efforts. Overall, this study highlights the significance of good governance, female labor force participation, and pro-poor and pro-growth public policies in addressing poverty. The findings emphasize the need for improved governance, increased female labor force participation, and policies promoting income equality and economic growth to effectively break the cycle of poverty within the country.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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